

Role of ultrasonication in fast and effective biohydrolysis of vegetable oil

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Abstract : The agitation plays an important role in the rate of hydrolysis of oil. Agitation causes the effective change in interfacial area between the oil phase and the aqueous phase and thereby influences the rate of hydrolysis. In this study, to compare the hydrolysis rates of oil, ultrasonication and mechanical agitations were used for interfacial area generation. By ultrasonication, larger interfacial area with much narrower distribution of oil droplet could be produced as compared to mechanical agitation. Experiments carried out to assess the hydrolysis rate of lipids, showed that ultrasonication significantly increases the interfacial area between oil and water saturated with enzyme and the specificity of enzymes was also not disturbed.

Keywords : Vegetable oil, lipase, biohydrolysis, fatty acids, ultrasonication.

Introduction

Fats and oils are glycerol esters of fatty acids, known as triacylglycerol (TAG). Hydrolysis can break down TAG and release the glycerol and fatty acids. Fatty acids (FA) are widely used in industry to produce various types of oleochemicals¹⁻³. The applications, importance and significance of lipases for the production of fatty acids from oils have already been established⁴⁻⁹. Biohydrolysis is an emerging technology in respect to reaction conditions and quality and quantity of fatty acid produced. Especially in case of polyunsaturated fatty acids, where high temperature is not at all desirable to protect the quality of the fatty acid, the mild reaction conditions of biohydrolysis are always preferable. The different specificities of different lipases permit the splitting of specific fatty acids from triacylglycerols, which cannot be obtained by conventional chemical procedures. Though in some cases, longer time needed for enzymatic hydrolysis may show a disadvantage of the process.

Water and oil are insoluble at low temperature, so the rate of hydrolysis reaction under normal circumstances is extremely slow. The reaction can only occur in the interfacial region between the two liquids. Increase in the temperature, the oil solubility in water increases and the speed of the reaction accelerates quickly. A vigorous mix-

ing is therefore could increase the area of contact between the two immiscible phases, and this produces an emulsion. Lipases, as protein molecules, help in producing the emulsion and also hydrolyze TAG and related moieties when emulsified. But the high speeds can result in increased shear rate on the lipase molecules and lead to denaturation of the enzyme resulting in reduced activity¹⁰.

In ultrasonication, the power supply converts DC voltage to high frequency (25 kHz) electrical energy. This electrical energy is transmitted to the transducer where it is changed to mechanical vibrations. The vibrations from the transducer are intensified by a probe, which radiates the acoustic energy into the fluid, and thus creates pressure waves in the liquid. Sound waves consist of alternating expansion and compression cycles. The compression phase exerts positive pressure in the medium, while expansion results from the negative pressure phase. This produces millions of microscopic bubbles (cavities) in a liquid or semi-liquid medium during the expansion cycle (negative pressure excursion) and implodes violently during the positive excursion. It is this phenomenon, referred to as cavitations, which produces the powerful shearing, causing the molecules in the liquid to become intensely agitated. The intensity with which cavitations takes

place in a liquid medium varies greatly with the properties of that medium, which include vapour pressure, surface tension, viscosity, and density, as well as any other property that is related to the number of atoms, ions, or molecules in the medium. The energy required to form a cavitation bubble in a liquid is proportional to both surface tension and vapour pressure. Thus, higher the surface tension of a liquid, the greater will be the energy required to produce a cavitation bubble. Consequently, greater will be the shockwave energy that is produced when the bubble collapses. The intensity of ultrasonic power is usually measured by the duty cycle, which is measured by the frequency of cycle repetitions.

The applicability of power ultrasound for dispersion, and specially emulsification purposes has been known for long although in most cases application is still restricted to laboratory scale¹¹. Currently, ultrasonic emulsification is gaining interest in many industrial fields, as a better alternative to conventional emulsification processes. These fields include water processing, powder production, protection against insects, combustion of fuels, cleaning, surface hindering, impregnation and coating, complex vibration testing, post-thermal treatment of hardened steels, founding and casting, and many more¹²⁻¹⁴. Ultrasonic influence in such situations is much more effective than mechanical stirrers. In 1995, Mason first reported¹⁵ hydrolysis of immiscible liquids, oils in aqueous NaOH, using ultrasonication. He reported that low frequency ultrasonication is a useful tool for emulsification of immiscible liquids. Later, Li *et al.*¹³ studied the enzymatic hydrolysis of a variety of pulps for its enhancement with continuous ultrasonic irradiation. They proposed a model for the enhancement effect of the ultrasonic irradiation on the enzymatic hydrolysis of cellulose. Later, Freitas *et al.*¹⁶ have demonstrated a continuous contact and contamination free ultrasonic emulsification system. Using this system, they could generate vegetable-oil-in water emulsions with droplet size of 0.5 μ m and below with good reproducibility. Though many applications of ultrasound for generating fine dispersions of oil in water have been demonstrated, very few have used it to study its effect on the enzymatic hydrolysis of oils. Ramchandran *et al.*¹⁷ first used ultrasonic emulsification to generate oil-water emulsions to hydrolyse the oil. A comparative study of enzymatic hydrolysis of soyabean oil with and without ultrasonic agitation along with specificity study of the enzymes is presented in this report with a simple experimental procedure.

Results and discussion

The present study was carried out to obtain a comparative data of fat hydrolysis with one immobilized (TLIM) and two crude lipases (AY amano and G amano) by magnetic stirring and ultrasonic agitation. By magnetic stirring the crude enzymes were able to hydrolyze the oil up to the acid value 5.6 to 7.8 respectively in 15 min where as the immobilized lipase hydrolyzed the oil up to acid value of 6.4 and up to 71 in 6 h with same enzyme and water concentration (Fig. 1). The same experiment when carried out with ultrasonic agitation, the extent of enzymatic hydrolysis was increased almost five folds in case of all crude and immobilized lipases in the same time span while maintaining the same enzyme and water concentration (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Comparative data of acid value after 15 min hydrolysis.

When comparative time study was done with the same reaction mixture, it was seen that ultrasonication yielded almost same result in 40 min, which was obtained by 6 h of continuous stirring of the reaction mixture at 55 ± 5 °C by magnetic stirrer (Fig. 2). The gas-chromatographic profile of the crude oil and the fatty acid produced in each step did not vary appreciably with each other as in the case of first two random lipases where as position specific TLIM produced fatty acids of some what different kinds (Table 1).

Experimental

Materials :

Refined Soyabean Oil of Adani Wilmer Co. Ltd. was procured from local market. Three types of solid enzymes

Fig. 2. Comparative data of acid value with time using lipase TLIM and with and without ultrasonic agitation.

the oil up to 66%. The other two are soluble lipases AY amano and G amano, which were also gift from M/s Amano Enzyme Inc., Japan. These are random lipases. They could hydrolyse the oil completely.

All reagents used were of analytical grade.

Ultrasonic horn :

Make : Vibronics

Frequency : 15 kHz

Rated output power : 120 W

Diameter of the stainless

steel tip of the horn : 2.42×10^{-3} m

Surface area of ultra-sound irradiating face : 4.52×10^{-6} m²

Experimental procedure :

The sketch of the experimental setup is presented in the Scheme 1.

Table 1. Gas-chromatographic profile of the crude oil and the fatty acid produced

Sample	Fatty acid (% w/w)				
	C _{16:0}	C _{18:0}	C _{18:1}	C _{18:2}	C _{18:3}
Soyabean oil	10.5	5.1	23.3	55.0	6.5
Fatty acid produced in 15 min with enzyme AY Amano					
with mechanical stirring	11.7	5.5	22.6	54.2	6.0
with ultrasonic stirring	10.7	5.3	23.1	55.0	6.3
Fatty acid produced in 15 min with enzyme GY Amano					
with mechanical stirring	11.6	5.6	22.7	54.4	6.1
with ultrasonic stirring	10.6	5.4	23.1	54.8	6.3
Fatty acid produced in 15 min with enzyme TLIM					
with mechanical stirring	12.8	5.6	22.8	52.0	6.1
with ultrasonic stirring	15.8	7.2	21.7	49.0	6.4
Fatty acid produced in 40 min with enzyme TLIM					
with mechanical stirring	13.5	6.8	22.1	51.8	6.2
with ultrasonic stirring	18.3	7.5	18.7	49.1	6.4
Fatty acid produced in 60 min with enzyme TLIM					
with mechanical stirring	13.7	5.9	22.2	53.8	6.4
with ultrasonic stirring	19.0	7.6	18.5	48.6	6.3

were used in this study. The first enzyme, enzyme (TLIM) was a gift from M/s Novozymes India Ltd., Bangalore. It is *Thermomyces lanuginosa* lipase immobilized on silica gel. It is a position specific lipase so it could hydrolyze

Equal sets of reactants were prepared of each batch, for conventional stirring using magnetic stirrer at 200 rpm and also for ultrasonic mixing. Each set consists of refined SBO and distilled water in 1 : 6 molar ratio and

Scheme 1

lipase, 10% (w/w) in case of immobilized enzyme and 2% (w/w) in case of crude enzymes on the basis of total substrate weight. In case of magnetic stirring, the temperature of the reactant was kept at 55 ± 5 °C. The first phase of hydrolysis was done for 15 min and then it was continued for 6 h.

In case of ultrasonic mixing the reaction mixture was treated without heating using a fixed ultrasound power of 120 W from an ultrasonic horn. Approximately 100 ml of oil was placed in the flask and treated for 15, 30 and 40 min with ultrasonic irradiation. Sonication was achieved at low frequencies of 15 kHz. The temperature was maintained around 55–60 °C by the in-site generated heat. After 15 min of sonication, the reaction mixture was cooled and again placed under irradiation. The reaction vessel was well circulated by hand to cover the total surface.

The reaction was continued for 40 min (step wise : 15 + 15 + 10). The tip of the horn was set at the oil-water interface.

All the experiments were made in duplicate and average data are presented.

Determination of acid value :

During the hydrolysis reaction of oil, the fatty acids are released and the acidity of the reaction mixture rises and therefore determination of acid value can be used as a measure of the rate of hydrolysis.

The samples were drawn time to time from different sets of reactions and the lipid part was extracted with hexane, dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate. After evaporating the solvent completely, sample was weighed and acid value was measured¹⁸.

GC analysis :

Gas-liquid chromatography (GC) was employed for determining the fatty acid composition of the oil and fatty acid obtained after their conversion into corresponding methyl esters¹⁹. The GC (make : Agilent, model : 6890

N) instrument used was equipped with FID detector and capillary DB-Wax column (30 m L × 0.25 m I.D.). N₂, H₂ and airflow rate was maintained at 1 ml/min, 30 ml/min and 300 ml/min respectively. Inlet and detector temperature was kept at 250 °C and the oven temperature was programmed as 150–190–230 °C with increase rate of 15 °C/min and 5 min hold up to 150 °C and 4 °C/min with 10 min hold up to 230 °C.

Conclusion :

Ultrasonic irradiation proved suitable for efficient hydrolysis of vegetable oils since relatively simple devices can be used to perform the reaction. The highest conversion was achieved with short residence time. The results confirm the applicability of ultrasonicator as a better alternative to mechanical agitation for increased rate of hydrolysis of lipids by lipase.

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